

The Administrators' Ethical Leadership and Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

Arlyn V. Maratas

Abstract. The teaching quality of educators is of utmost importance. However, the effectiveness of teachers is not solely determined by their individual capabilities but is influenced by ethical leadership demonstrated by school administrators which has been recognized as a potential catalyst for enhancing teaching quality. This study utilized a non-experimental quantitative research methodology using a descriptive correlation approach was applied. Statistical analyses such as the mean, Pearson R correlation, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized. The participants in the research were one hundred twenty (120) public secondary school educators conveniently selected secondary schools in Compostela East District at Compostela, Davao De Oro. Descriptive results of the study revealed that the administrators' ethical leadership and the quality of teaching in public secondary schools both obtained high descriptive level rating which means that these parameters of the study are oftentimes evident. Consequently, the inferential results of the study suggested that it rejected its set null hypothesis since there is a significant relationship between administrators' ethical leadership and quality of teaching in public secondary schools. Likewise, the regression analysis resulted that fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others as indicators of administrators' ethical leadership significantly influenced the quality of teaching in public secondary schools.

KEY WORDS

1. Administrators Ethical Leadership 2. Quality of Teaching 3. Public Secondary School Teachers

1. Introduction

The quality of education is a paramount concern in the development of nations, and it is widely acknowledged that teachers play a critical role in shaping the educational experiences and outcomes of students. In the context of public secondary schools, where diverse student populations seek knowledge and skills for their future, the teaching quality of educators is of utmost importance. However, the effectiveness of teachers is not solely determined by their individual capabilities but is influenced by various factors within the educational environment. One critical factor is the ethical leadership demonstrated by school administrators which has been recognized as a potential catalyst for enhancing teaching quality. Administrators who lead with fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others can positively influence the work environment and professional development opportunities for teachers. In many ASEAN nations, school leaders may not receive adequate preparation in ethical leadership practices, leading to a lack of clarity regarding their roles in fostering ethical

behavior and creating a positive educational environment (Dawson Velamuri, 2017). Another significant issue is the presence of corruption and nepotism within educational institutions in some ASEAN countries. The Transparency International Bribery Index (2020) highlights the prevalence of bribery and corruption in the education sector in certain nations. Such unethical practices can erode trust in leadership, compromise decision-making processes, and ultimately impact the quality of education. In addition, external pressures, including political interference, can compromise the autonomy of school leaders and impact their ability to make ethical decisions that enhance teaching quality (Gamage, 2016). In the Philippines, teaching quality is a subject of great importance as the nation strives to provide equitable and effective education for all. The Department of Education (DepEd) places a strong emphasis on the competencies of public secondary school teachers, which include content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and student engagement. These dimensions align with DepEd's vision of producing globally competitive graduates (DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2019). Consequently, school administrators, such as principals and department heads, hold positions of authority and responsibility. Their leadership style and ethical conduct have far-reaching implications for the school environment, teacher morale, and, consequently, the quality of education (Luna De Guia, 2017). However, these phenomena were threatened due to several issues such as some Philippine schools face ethical challenges such as corruption, nepotism, and favoritism, which can undermine trust in leadership and hinder the effectiveness of teachers (Aragon, 2019). Addressing these ethical issues is paramount to ensure that teachers are not discouraged or demotivated, ultimately improving the quality of education. Moreover, ethical leadership practices can significantly impact the professional development and job satisfaction of teachers. A lack of ethical leadership may result in arbitrary decision-making, favoritism in promotions, and a lack of transparency in resource allocation (Ng Leng, 2019). When teachers perceive that their leaders do not act ethically or fairly, it can affect their morale and job satisfaction, which, in turn, may affect their dedication to providing quality education. Conversely, ethical leadership practices, such as fairness, accountability, and empathy, can create a positive work environment that promotes teacher well-being and, consequently, enhances teaching quality (Brown Treviño, 2016). Furthermore, while prior research has explored the impact of leadership on educational outcomes, limited empirical evidence exists on the specific relationship between administrators' ethical leadership and the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers, especially concerning the dimensions of content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and student engagement. Therefore, this study aims to bridge this research gap and provide insights into the potential influence of ethical leadership practices on teaching quality in the context of public secondary education.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods in conducting the study which are considered strategies or techniques utilized in the collection of data evidence for analysis in order to uncover new information or create better understanding of a topic. Contents of this chapter include the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. *Research Design*—In this study, the researcher used a descriptive correlational method for non-experimental quantitative research. The descriptive design explains the researched population, circumstance, or phenomena. It emphasizes on addressing the how, what, when, and where questions rather than the why of a research topic (Babbie, 2016). This design is important to the research because it specifies the techniques and processes for gathering the necessary information, as well as the general operational pattern or framework of the project, which dictates what information is to be acquired from which sources using which methods (Fox 2015). In particular, the descriptive part of the design will be used in assessing the extent of administrator’s ethical leadership as well as the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers of Compostela East District, Division of Davao de Oro. On the other hand, the correlational research design part of this study is a methodological approach used in scientific research to examine the relationships or associations between two or more variables. It aims to determine whether changes in one variable are associated with changes in another variable without establishing causation. In a correlational study, researchers collect data on the variables of interest and then use statistical techniques to analyze the strength and direction of the relationships between these variables (Bordens, 2019). Particularly, this study will employ the said design since it wants to determine the significant relationship between the administrator’s ethical leadership and teaching quality of public secondary school teachers as well as prove if there is an indicator of administrator’s ethical leadership that significantly influence the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The conduct of this study was held on the selected secondary schools in Compostela East District in Compostela, Davao De Oro. There were one hundred

and twenty (120) secondary level educators that will serve as the responders in this research. The respondents were selected using a convenience sampling, which is the most common method of selection that does not rely on probability, will be used to choose them. This type of sampling method is used for collecting samples that involves getting samples from sources of data that are easily located or that provide researchers convenience (Edgar and Manz, 2017).

2.3. *Research Instrument*—Developing research instruments is a critical step in the research process as they serve as the means to collect data and gather information from participants. These instruments play a pivotal role in ensuring the quality and validity of research findings. Well-designed research instruments help researchers measure variables accurately, leading to reliable data (Babbie, 2016). Moreover, they allow for the standardization of data collection, enabling the replication of studies and comparison of results across different contexts (Neuman, 2014). In this investigation, the researcher used a survey questionnaire as its instrument in gathering its data. The survey questionnaire will have two parts that would cater the two variables in the study. Relatively, careful instrument development also promotes construct validity by ensuring that the items or questions included align with the intended constructs or concepts under investigation (DeVellis, 2017). Additionally, clear and concise research instruments enhance participants’ understanding and cooperation, which is crucial for obtaining high-quality data (Dillman et al., 2014). Ultimately, the development of research instruments contributes to the credibility and rigor of research findings, making it an essential aspect of the research process. Specifically, validity of the instrument will be assured by research expert and members of the panel committee. The survey instrument also was subjected for pilot testing in order to determine its reliability. The pilot testing was done with 50 respondents on

top of the respondents of the study. This computed Cronbach's Alpha after the pilot testing is 0.726 which mean that the instrument is reliable. For the first part of the survey instrument, this would provide data on the administrator's ethical leadership. Questions from this part of the instrument were adopted from the Graphical Inventory of Ethical Leadership (GIEL) Scale

by Sparks Graves (2015). In the process of interpreting its data, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The administrator's ethical leadership is always evident.
3.40-4.19	High	The administrator's ethical leadership is often evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The administrator's ethical leadership is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Low	The administrator's ethical leadership is seldom evident.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The administrator's ethical leadership is not evident.

For the second part of the questionnaire, this will determine the data on the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. In this part, the researcher adopted OECD (2008) Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS). The same with the first part of the survey questionnaire, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey

having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest in interpreting its data. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	The teaching quality of public secondary school teachers is always evident.
3.40-4.19	High	The teaching quality of public secondary school teachers is often evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	The teaching quality of public secondary school teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Low	The teaching quality of public secondary school teachers is seldom evident.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	The teaching quality of public secondary school teachers is never evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure—*

At the outset of the data gathering procedure, the researcher wrote a letter seeking permission from the Dean of the Graduate School so that this research study will be conducted. Next, the researcher secured a letter asking for permission to the Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Davao De Oro through the channels of the Office of Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS) of the selected different schools. Upon approval of the permit, the survey questionnaire will be ready for the conduct of the study. During the conduct of the study, the researcher personally hand-in the sur-

vey questionnaire to the selected respondents. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents will be done answering the survey questions. The researcher ensured that the collection and retrieval of data was conducted following the IATF protocols for face-to-face learning delivery mode. Lastly, the collected data was analyzed by a statistician using the different measures of treating the data as presented this chapter. The results in the treatment of the data were interpreted for further information of the study.

2.5. Data Analysis—The study used the respondents' collected data for analysis. The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: The mean is commonly used to measure the central tendency to be used in analyzing the mean scores of administrator's ethical leadership and the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers for SOP 1 and SOP 2. The Pearson R correlation to measure the relationship between the administrator's ethical

leadership and the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers for SOP 3. This can assess the strength and direction of associations between ethical leadership indicators (fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, respect for others) and teaching quality indicators (content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, student engagement). The Multiple Regression Analysis (MLR) can be used to determine which specific indicators of ethical leadership have the most substantial influence on teaching quality.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions based on the data gathered after the conduct of this study. This includes the interpretation of the data and the repercussions of the findings of the study. The deliberations presented in this chapter are aligned to the statement of the problem cited in the previous chapters of this study. Specifically, the presentation for the results and discussions will started from the extent of administrators' ethical leadership as perceived by public secondary teachers in terms of fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others. This was followed by the presentation of the level of teaching quality of public secondary school teachers as well as its indicators such as the content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and student engagement. Next, was the discussion of the results of the significant relationship between the extent of administrators' ethical leadership and teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. Lastly, the discussion of results on which indicator of administrators' ethical leadership such as fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others significantly influence the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers.

Summary of the Extent of Administrator’s Ethical Leadership as Perceived by Public Secondary School Teachers

Shown in Table 1 is the summary statistical result for the extent of administrators’ ethical leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers as well as its indicators such as fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others. Administrators’ ethical leadership makes them responsible for shaping the educational experiences of students, creating a positive school climate, and ensuring the fair and equitable treatment of all stakeholders, in-

cluding students, teachers, parents, and the community at large (Larrivee, 2018). With this, ethical educational leadership involves a commitment to ethical conduct, integrity, transparency, and a focus on the best interests of students’ academic and moral development (Bredeson Johansson, 2013). In addition, administrators are expected to create a culture of trust and respect within their schools, where ethical behavior is not only taught but also practiced. This includes addressing issues of fairness, equity, and inclusivity, and ensuring that all students have equal access to quality education (Starratt, 2016).

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Administrator’s Ethical Leadership as Perceived by Public Secondary School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Fairness and Justice	4.00	High
Empathy	3.67	High
Accountability	3.57	High
Respect for Others	3.84	High
Overall	3.77	High

Summary of the Level of the Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

Shown in Table 2 is the summary statistical result for the level of the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers as well as its indicators such as the content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, classroom management, and student engagement. Teaching quality involves ongoing professional development and

a commitment to reflective practice. Effective teachers continuously seek opportunities to improve their teaching skills, stay updated on educational research, and adapt their practices to meet changing student needs (Ingersoll Strong, 2015). Reflective practice allows teachers to assess their teaching methods and make adjustments based on feedback and self-assessment.

Table 2. Summary of the Level of the Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Content Knowledge	4.02	High
Pedagogical Knowledge	3.86	High
Classroom Management	3.91	High
Student Engagement	4.16	High
Overall	3.99	High

Based on the analysis in the above table, the overall mean rating of the level of teaching quality obtained a mean rating score of 3.99. This numerical data result is equivalent to a “high” descriptive level rating which means that the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers is often evident. This further suggests that public secondary school teachers, as perceived by respondents, consistently exhibit qualities associated with effective teaching. Relatively, literature on teacher effectiveness underscores the multifaceted nature of high-quality teaching. Effective teachers not only deliver content effectively but also foster a positive classroom climate, differentiate instruction to meet diverse student needs, and continually engage in professional development (Darling-Hammond, 2017). In addition, the high mean rating for the overall level of teaching quality reflects the consensus in the literature that effective teaching goes beyond the transmission of knowledge and involves creating a dynamic learning environment that supports student growth and development. Specifically, all the indicators under the teaching quality of public secondary teachers obtained a “high” verbal equivalent rating. This means that all indicators of teaching quality of public secondary teachers is often evident. The data in Table 10 as well as the presentation in the above paragraphs revealed a clear picture of the various factors that contribute to teaching quality of public secondary teachers in the classroom.

Significant Relationship between the Administrator’s Ethical Leadership and Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

One of the aims of this study is to investigate the correlation between the administrators’ ethical leadership and the level of teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is a suitable statistical analysis method for examining the presented data, as it is commonly employed to assess the presence of a significant associa-

tion between the means of two distinct groups (Creswell Poth, 2016). The significance level for this study is established at 0.05. Shown in Table 3 is the analysis result on the correlation between the administrators’ ethical leadership and teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. The correlation analysis reveals a strong positive and statistically significant association between the administrators’ ethical leadership and teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. The correlation coefficient (r -value) is determined to be 0.759, indicating a strong positive relationship. Additionally, the p -value is calculated to be 0.000, further confirming the significance of the link between the two variables. This means that the strong positive correlation underscores the importance of ethical leadership as a key factor influencing the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. Therefore, the null hypothesis posited in this study, which states that there is no statistically significant correlation between the administrators’ ethical leadership and teaching quality of public secondary school teachers, is rejected. This study’s correlational analysis further suggests that when teachers acknowledge the presence of ethical leadership of their administrators, there is a corresponding rise in teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. This finding is consistent with the broader understanding that effective leadership practices, including ethical considerations, contribute significantly to shaping the organizational culture and fostering a conducive environment for teaching and learning (Leithwood Jantzi, 2018). In addition, the literature cited in this study further supports the notion that ethical leadership is associated with improved teacher morale, commitment, and job satisfaction (Brown Treviño, 2016). When administrators model ethical behavior and prioritize fairness and justice, teachers are more likely to feel supported and motivated in their roles. Ethical leadership contributes to a positive work envi-

ronment where teachers are encouraged to excel, dedication (Harris, 2013).
fostering a sense of professional fulfillment and

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the Administrator’s Ethical Leadership and Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

Administrator’s Ethical Leadership	Teaching Quality	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Fairness and Justice		0.660	.000	Reject
Empathy		0.524	.000	Reject
Accountability		0.516	.000	Reject
Respect for Others		0.634	.000	Reject
Overall		0.759	.000	Reject

Moreover, research on leadership in education emphasizes the role of ethical leaders in shaping the values and norms of the school community, creating a climate conducive to effective teaching and learning (Waters, Marzano McNulty, 2018). Ethical leaders promote trust and collaboration among staff, which, in turn, enhances the overall effectiveness of educational institutions (Harris, 2013). Furthermore, the inferential correlational analysis in Table 11 highlighted also the relationship between each indicator of administrators’ ethical leadership and quality of teaching in public secondary schools. The analysis result presented shows that there are significant correlations between each indicator of administrators’ ethical leadership and quality of teaching in public secondary schools. Ranking correlational analysis with its correlation r-value, the correlation between fairness and justice of administrators’ ethical leadership quality of teaching in public secondary schools came first with an r-value equal to 0.660 and a p-value equal to 0.000. This means that there is a strong positive correlation between these two parameters. This further suggests that the perception of fairness and justice in administrators’ ethical leadership significantly contributes to the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. The identified strong positive correlation between the fairness and justice aspect of administrators’ ethical leadership and the

quality of teaching in public secondary schools aligns with existing literature emphasizing the crucial role of fairness and justice in educational leadership. When administrators prioritize fairness and justice, it creates an environment where teachers feel valued and supported, leading to increased commitment and motivation (Leithwood Jantzi, 2018). Additionally, research suggests that fairness and justice in educational leadership positively impact student outcomes. A fair and just school environment is linked to improved student behavior, engagement, and academic achievement (Thapa, Cohen, Guffey, Higgins-D’Alessandro, 2013;). Administrators who prioritize equity and inclusivity in their leadership practices create a culture that fosters a sense of belonging and equality among students and teachers alike (Wong Wong, 2018).

Regression Analysis of the Administrator’s Ethical Leadership on the Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

The last objective of this study is to determine which indicators of administrators’ ethical leadership significantly influence the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. The Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) is best fit for this analysis since this statistical treatment is defined as a predictive analysis which is used to explain the relationship between one continuous dependent variable and two or more indepen-

dent variables (Trek, 2019). Still, this data analysis is set with an alpha equal to 0.05. Based on the MLR analysis presented in Table 4, the overall statistical analysis of the study came up with a value of F that was 44.828 and a value of 0.000 for the p-value which is higher than the set critical value. This means that the administrators' ethical leadership has a significant influence on the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. This further implies that the regression analysis used in the study is useful

which means that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. This finding aligns with established literature of the study which emphasize the pivotal role of leadership in shaping the educational environment and outcomes (Robinson, Lloyd, Rowe, 2018). Effective ethical leadership involves creating a positive organizational culture, setting clear expectations, and fostering collaboration, all of which contribute to improved teaching practices (Bass Riggio, 2016).

Table 4. Regression Analysis of the Administrator's Ethical Leadership on the Teaching Quality of Public Secondary School Teachers

Administrator's Ethical Leadership	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients (Beta)	t	Sig.	Decision on H0
(Constant)	1.072	0.234		4.588	.000	
Fairness and Justice	0.303	0.048	.429	6.323	.000	Reject
Empathy	0.215	0.057	.238	3.315	.001	Reject
Accountability	0.251	0.059	.269	3.572	.000	Reject
Respect for Others	0.231	0.053	.321	4.362	.000	Reject

R = .881; R² = .776; F-value = 44.828; p-value = .000

Moreover, this study revealed that all the indicators of the administrators' ethical leadership as declared in this study such as the fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others have all significant influence on the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. Each of these elements positively correlates with the quality of teaching in public secondary schools, rejecting the initial null hypothesis that posited no significant influence of these factors. Specifically, fairness and justice indicator of administrators' ethical leadership ranked on top obtaining a t-value equivalent of 6.323 and a p-value equal to .000. This was followed the respect for others indicator obtaining a t-value equivalent of 4.362 and a p-value equal to .000. Next is the accountability indicator obtaining a t-value equivalent of 3.572 and a p-value equal to .000. Lastly, is the empathy indicator obtaining a t-value equivalent of 3.315 and a p-value equal to .001. Furthermore, the analysis of the study employs Multiple Linear

Regression (MLR) to determine the influence of various aspects of the administrators' ethical leadership on the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. One of the key metrics derived from this statistical treatment is the coefficient of determination, denoted as R², which stands at 0.776. This high R² value indicates that the analysis has a 77.60 percent predictive power for explaining the variation of the quality of teaching in public secondary schools based on the factors considered in this study. In other words, the substantial coefficient of determination R² at nearly 78 percent such as the one observed in this study, reinforces the idea that administrators' ethical leadership is a key determinant in explaining the variation in teaching quality, emphasizing the substantial impact of leadership practices on educational outcomes. This aligns with established literature emphasizing the influential role of ethical leadership in educational settings. Previous researches suggested that leadership practices significantly contribute

to educational outcomes, with ethical leadership playing a crucial role in shaping school climate, teacher morale, and overall student success (Waters, Marzano McNulty, 2018). However, the R² value also leaves approximately 22.4 percent of the variance unexplained. This suggests that while the administrators' ethical leadership is highly significant, it's not the only set of variables affecting quality of teaching in public secondary schools. This remaining variance could be attributed to additional factors of the administrators' ethical leadership that were not covered in the study. The acknowledgment of unexplained variance underscores

the complexity of factors influencing the quality of teaching in public secondary schools beyond the variables considered in the study on administrators' ethical leadership. This resonates with existing literature highlighting the various nature of educational outcomes and the diverse range of factors that contribute to teaching effectiveness. Previous researches cited in this study indicates that educational environments are influenced by a countless of interconnected factors, including school culture, community engagement, and external policy factors, which can impact teaching quality (Robinson, Lloyd, Rowe, 2018).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings of the study based on the outcome of the gathered data. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—In the context of public secondary schools, where diverse student populations seek knowledge and skills for their future, the teaching quality of educators is of utmost importance. However, the effectiveness of teachers is not solely determined by their individual capabilities but is influenced by various factors within the educational environment. One critical factor is the ethical leadership demonstrated by school administrators which has been recognized as a potential catalyst for enhancing teaching quality. In this study, a non-experimental quantitative research methodology using a descriptive correlation approach was applied. Statistical analyses such as the mean, Pearson R correlation, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized. The participants in the research were one hundred twenty (120) public secondary school educators on selected secondary schools in Compostela East District in Compostela, Davao De Oro. These respondents were chosen via a sample process

known as convenience sampling. Data were analyzed based on the survey questionnaires that were used by the researcher after they had been modified to conform to the parameters of the study, which had been subjected to validation by experts and had its reliability examined. Descriptive results of the study revealed that the administrators' ethical leadership and the quality of teaching in public secondary schools both obtained high descriptive level rating which means that these parameters of the study are oftentimes evident. Consequently, the inferential results of the study suggested that it rejected its set null hypothesis since there is a significant relationship between administrators' ethical leadership and quality of teaching in public secondary schools. Likewise, the regression analysis resulted that fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others as indicators of administrators' ethical leadership significantly influenced the quality of teaching in public secondary schools.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: Public secondary school teachers perceived administrators' ethical leadership at a high level, which means that administrator's ethical leadership is often evident. This further suggests that administrators play a substantial role in shaping the educational environment, influencing teaching quality. Notably, the fairness and justice indicator ranked highest, emphasizing the importance of addressing issues related to bias, discrimination, and resource disparities, reflecting a commitment to equitable education. The respect for others indicator, ranking second, underscores administrators' recognition of diverse perspectives and contributions. Additionally, empathy though third, indicates administrators' efforts to create a nurturing environment. Lastly, the accountability indicator, while in the last place, still attains a high rating, portraying administrators as consistently upholding ethical standards and being perceived as embodying accountability traits by public secondary school teachers. Consequently, the public secondary school teachers are perceived to consistently exhibit high levels of teaching quality. This suggests that teachers, consistently demonstrate qualities associated with effective teaching. Notably, the leading indicator is student engagement, emphasizing the teachers' adeptness in creating engaging classroom environments. Following closely is content knowledge indicating that teachers often possess substantial subject matter expertise. The classroom management indicator ranks third signaling that public secondary school teachers frequently demonstrate effective classroom management skills crucial for a conducive learning atmosphere. Interestingly, pedagogical knowledge ranks last, though still at a high level, suggesting that, while it may be comparatively rated lower, teachers often exhibit sound pedagogical knowledge. Overall, the findings underscore the commendable teaching quality of public secondary school

teachers across various dimensions, highlighting their competence in creating engaging, well-managed, and knowledgeable learning environments. Moreover, there is a statistically significant positive correlation between administrators' ethical leadership and the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. The strong positive correlation emphasizes the critical role of ethical leadership as an influential factor shaping the quality of teaching in these educational settings. The findings suggest that an environment characterized by ethical leadership attributes positively contributes to the overall effectiveness of teaching. When teachers perceive and acknowledge the presence of ethical leadership in their administrators, there is a corresponding improvement in the quality of teaching among public secondary school educators. This highlights the interconnectedness between ethical leadership practices and the educational outcomes, reinforcing the importance of fostering ethical leadership within school leadership structures for the enhancement of teaching quality. Furthermore, there is a significant influence of administrators' ethical leadership on the quality of teaching in public secondary schools. Specific indicators of ethical leadership—fairness and justice, empathy, accountability, and respect for others—as individually and collectively contributing to the quality of teaching. The rejection of the null hypothesis emphasizes the positive correlation between these ethical leadership elements and teaching quality, underscoring their importance in shaping educational outcomes. The coefficient of determination (R^2) reinforces the substantial impact of administrators' ethical leadership, with a high predictive power explaining the variation in teaching quality based on the considered factors. However, the unexplained variance of approximately 22.4

4.3. *Recommendations*—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: The recommendations for

the Department of Education officials encompass several key areas. Firstly, addressing the high perception of administrators' ethical leadership among public secondary school teachers, it is recommended to prioritize ongoing professional development for administrators, emphasizing fairness, justice, respect, empathy, and accountability. Secondly, acknowledging the consistently high levels of teaching quality perceived by teachers, investment in professional development programs is recommended, specifically targeting pedagogical knowledge. Emphasis is placed on reinforcing pedagogical skills and creating platforms for collaborative knowledge-sharing among teachers to promote effective classroom management. Thirdly, given the statistically significant positive correlation between administrators' ethical leadership and teaching quality, the Department is urged to prioritize leadership training emphasizing ethical principles. Encouraging administrators to prioritize fairness, empathy, and accountability through recognition and rewards can positively impact teaching quality. Lastly, to leverage the substantial influence of administrators' ethical leadership, integration of ethical principles into training and evaluations is suggested. School administrators are recommended to prioritize the enhancement of ethical leadership based on the study's findings. This involves actively fostering fairness, justice, respect for others, empathy, and accountability, with a focus on reinforcing accountability practices to consistently uphold ethical standards. Moreover, administrators should facilitate professional development programs concentrating on pedagogical knowledge to complement existing strengths in student engagement and content knowledge. Encouraging knowledge-sharing among teachers and collaborative initiatives can promote effective classroom management strategies. Emphasizing ethical leadership principles in leadership training programs can lead to enhanced teaching quality by creating environments prioritizing fairness, empathy, and accountability. Acknowledging and rewarding ethical leadership practices can further motivate administrators to uphold these values. Integrating ethical leadership principles into training curricula and evaluations, along with continuous assessment mechanisms, ensures a consistent exhibition of ethical traits, positively impacting teaching quality. Public secondary teachers should actively embrace the study's insights to guide their professional growth. Acknowledging the prevalent perception of administrators' ethical leadership, teachers are urged to collaborate with administrators to cultivate fairness, justice, and accountability in the school environment. Encouraging ongoing dialogues on issues of bias, discrimination, and resource disparities can foster an equitable educational setting. Despite already exhibiting high teaching quality, teachers can focus on enhancing pedagogical knowledge, leveraging collaborative initiatives for knowledge-sharing among peers. Recognizing the positive correlation between administrators' ethical leadership and teaching quality, teachers should actively contribute to the development of ethical leadership attributes. Appreciating and acknowledging ethical practices among administrators can contribute to a positive working atmosphere. Moreover, given the substantial influence of administrators' ethical leadership on teaching quality, teachers are prompted to actively participate in discussions and research exploring additional variables influencing teaching quality, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the complex dynamics within the teaching and learning environment. Students are urged to recognize the critical role of administrators' ethical leadership in shaping their educational journey. Acknowledging the perceived fairness, justice, and accountability exhibited by administrators, students are encouraged to actively engage in a positive school environment that values diversity and inclusivity. The focus on student engagement and teachers' con-

tent knowledge underscores the commitment to fostering stimulating and knowledgeable learning environments, and students are invited to contribute to this positive atmosphere through active participation and collaborative learning. Understanding the positive correlation between administrators' ethical leadership and teaching quality, students are prompted to appreciate the joint efforts of administrators and teachers in creating an effective and conducive learning environment. Future researchers are encouraged to delve deeper into the identified conclusions to enrich the understanding of administrators' ethical leadership and teaching quality in public secondary schools. Future researchers may explore the distinctions of fairness, justice, respect for others, empathy, and accountability indicators can provide a more detailed picture of how these traits influence the educational environment. Focusing on further investigations into the dynamics of student engagement, content knowledge, classroom management, and pedagogical knowledge can unveil specific strategies and approaches that contribute to teachers' effectiveness. Furthermore, future researcher can focus on uncovering the unexplained variance by identifying additional variables or dimensions of administrators' ethical leadership that were not considered in the study. A more comprehensive exploration of these aspects will contribute to refining educational practices and policies.

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